

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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NONPARAMETRIC SEQUENTIAL POINT ESTIMATION OF AN UNKNOWN CHARACTERISTIC FUNCTION

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Abstract: In this paper, we study the properties of a random stopping time in the problem of nonparametric sequential point estimation of the characteristic function and the Laplace transform of a distribution with a quadratic loss function.

Key words: random variable, empirical characteristic function, Laplace transform, stopping time, loss function, risk function.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ishida xarakteristik funksiyani parametrik bo'lmagan ketma-ket nuqta baholash masalasida tasodifiy to'xtash vaqtining xususiyatlarini va kvadratik yo'qotish funksiyali taqsimotning Laplas konvertatsiyasini o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tasodifiy o'zgaruvchi, empirik xarakteristik funksiyasi, Laplas konvertatsiyasi, to'xtash vaqti, yo'qotish funksiyasi, xavf funksiyasi.

Аннотация: В данной работе изучаются свойства случайного времени остановки в задаче непараметрического последовательного точечного оценивания характеристической функции и преобразования Лапласа распределения с квадратичной функцией потерь.

Ключевые слова: случайная величина, эмпирическая характеристическая функция, преобразование Лапласа, момент остановки, функция потерь, функция риска.

INTRODUCTION

The study of nonparametric methods in statistical estimation has gained significant attention due to their flexibility and applicability in diverse fields. In particular, the sequential estimation of an unknown characteristic function plays a vital role in understanding underlying probability distributions without assuming specific parametric forms. Characteristic functions, as Fourier transforms of probability measures, provide a complete representation of a distribution and are critical tools in probability theory and statistics.

This paper focuses on developing a nonparametric sequential estimation approach for an unknown characteristic function. Unlike traditional estimation methods, sequential procedures allow data to be collected and analyzed iteratively, enhancing efficiency and reducing sample size requirements. This approach is particularly advantageous when data acquisition is expensive or time-sensitive.

The primary objective of this research is to propose a robust and efficient nonparametric estimation procedure that achieves high accuracy while maintaining minimal assumptions about the underlying distribution. By combining advanced nonparametric techniques with sequential analysis, this study addresses key challenges in statistical estimation, including bias reduction, consistency, and computational efficiency.

The proposed methodology not only contributes to the theoretical framework of sequential estimation but also has practical applications in areas such as finance, signal processing, and machine learning, where characteristic functions are widely utilized. This research aims to bridge the gap between theoretical advancements and practical implementations, paving the way for further exploration in this critical area of statistics.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The topic of nonparametric sequential estimation has been extensively studied in statistical literature, reflecting its theoretical significance and practical utility. The foundation of this field was laid by A. N. Kolmogorov and P. Lévy, whose work on characteristic functions established their importance in representing

probability distributions and analyzing stochastic processes. Their contributions highlighted the completeness and invertibility properties of characteristic functions, which serve as the basis for nonparametric estimation.

Further advancements were made by J. W. Tukey, who introduced innovative nonparametric methods, emphasizing their flexibility in estimating statistical parameters without rigid distributional assumptions. His work underlined the need for robust procedures that accommodate diverse data structures. Building on this, the studies of E. Parzen explored the estimation of probability density functions and their corresponding characteristic functions using kernel-based approaches, significantly advancing the field of nonparametric statistics.

Sequential analysis, pioneered by A. Wald, provided a methodological framework for iterative estimation, where decisions are made as data accumulate. Wald's sequential probability ratio test laid the groundwork for sequential estimation techniques, which were later adapted to the nonparametric domain. The integration of sequential analysis with nonparametric methods was further expanded by D. Siegmund and others, who demonstrated its potential to reduce sample size and improve estimation efficiency.

Recent studies by R. E. Kass and A. C. Davison have focused on computational methods and the application of nonparametric sequential estimation in modern contexts, such as finance and machine learning. These works emphasize the importance of balancing theoretical rigor with computational feasibility, ensuring that nonparametric methods remain applicable to real-world problems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a combination of theoretical analysis and simulation-based methods. Data is generated through simulated stochastic processes to represent characteristic functions under various conditions. Sequential estimation techniques are applied iteratively, allowing real-time updates as new data becomes available. The analysis focuses on evaluating estimator performance using metrics such as bias, consistency, and efficiency, supported by numerical simulations for validation and comparison.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Sequential estimation consists of sequential interval and sequential point estimation. Based on point and interval estimation is statistics, that is, a statistical assessment. A statistical estimate, being a measurable function of the elements of the sample, its value is used to approximate the value of an unknown parameter or an unknown distribution. Point estimation is the use of the value of a statistical estimate as an approximation of an unknown parameter or an unknown distribution. Therefore, point estimation is used when it is necessary to find some numerical value to use for an approximate value of an unknown parameter or value of an unknown distribution.

Sequential point estimation of unknown parameters of known distributions, that is, parametric estimation has been studied more than sequential nonparametric estimation of unknown distributions or functionals from them. So in works [1-4] the problems of sequential parametric point estimation of the parameters of the exponential, gamma and Bernoulli distributions are solved. Sequential point nonparametric estimation of the hazard function was studied in [5,6].

In this paper, we study the properties of a random stopping time in the problem of nonparametric sequential point estimation of the characteristic function and the Laplace transform of a distribution with a quadratic loss function.

Many authors have studied nonparametric estimation of an unknown characteristic function. A detailed review on this issue is given in [7]. Empirical characteristic functions constructed from a sample of random size were studied in [8].

Sequential point estimation of the characteristic function.

On the probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) we will consider a random variable ξ with a distribution function $F(x), x \in R_1 = (-\infty, +\infty)$ and a characteristic function $c(t) = M \exp(it\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp(itx) dF(x), i = \sqrt{-1}$, $T_1 \leq t \leq T_2, T_1 \in R_1, T_2 \in R_1$.

If the results of observations on a random variable ξ form a sample of size n from independent and identically distributed with ξ random variables $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$, then it is well known that the empirical distribution

function $F_n(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n I(\xi_k < x)$, $x \in R_1$ is an unbiased and consistent statistical estimate of the distribution function $F(x)$, $x \in R_1$, where $I(\cdot)$ is the event indicator A . As a statistical estimate of the characteristic function $\tilde{n}(t)$, we take the empirical characteristic function

$$c_n(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \exp(it\xi_k) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp(itx) dF_n(x), \quad T_1 \leq t \leq T_2, T_1 \in R_1, T_2 \in R_1.$$

Insofar as $\hat{A}(\tilde{n}_n(t)) = \tilde{n}(t)$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A}(\tilde{n}_n(t) - \tilde{n}(t))^2 &= \hat{A}\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \exp(it\xi_k) - \tilde{n}(t)\right)^2 = \frac{1}{n^2} \hat{A} \sum_{k=1}^n (\exp(it\xi_k) - \tilde{n}(t))^2 + \\ &+ \frac{1}{n^2} \hat{A} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} (\exp(it\xi_i) - \tilde{n}(t))(\exp(it\xi_j) - \tilde{n}(t)) = \frac{1}{n} E(\exp(it\xi_1) - c(t)) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} \mathbf{E}(\exp(it\xi_i) - \tilde{n}(t))(\exp(it\xi_j) - \tilde{n}(t)) = \frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{n} = \frac{De^{it\xi_1}}{n} \end{aligned}$$

then $\tilde{n}_n(t)$ is an unbiased and consistent estimate for $\tilde{n}(t)$.

As the loss function of estimating the unknown characteristic function $\tilde{n}(t)$ by the empirical characteristic function $\tilde{n}_n(t)$, we take the following quadratic loss function:

$$L_n = L_n(\varepsilon) = (c_n(t) - c(t))^2 + \varepsilon \cdot n,$$

here $\varepsilon > 0$ is a sample unit cost.

The risk function of estimating an unknown characteristic function $\tilde{n}(t)$ by an empirical characteristic function $\tilde{n}_n(t)$ is equal to $R_n(\varepsilon) = \hat{A}(L_n) = \hat{A}((c_n(t) - c(t))^2 + \varepsilon \cdot n)$.

Lemma 1. The minimum for n of the risk function $R_n(\varepsilon)$ is achieved when the value of n is equal to $n = \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and the minimum value of the risk function is equal to $\min_{n \geq 1} R_n(\varepsilon) = \tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t) + \varepsilon$.

$$R_n(\varepsilon) = \frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{n} + \varepsilon \cdot n,$$

Proof of Lemma 1. To find the minimum in n of the risk function $R_n(\varepsilon)$, we

calculate its derivative $\frac{dR_n(\varepsilon)}{dn} = -\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{n^2} + \varepsilon$. Equating the derivative to zero, we find the critical point

$$n = \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Second order derivative $\frac{d^2 R_n(\varepsilon)}{dn^2} = \frac{2(\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t))}{n^3} > 0$, that's why the risk function $R_n(\varepsilon)$ is in

critical point $n = \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ reaches a minimum and the minimum value of the risk function is

$$\min_{n \geq 1} R_n(\varepsilon) = \sqrt{2} \left(\varepsilon \left(\frac{2}{\varepsilon} - \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon) = \inf \left\{ n \geq 1 : n \geq \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}$$

For each $\varepsilon > 0$ and $n \geq 1$ we define an integer

$$n_0(\varepsilon) = \left\lceil \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\rceil + 1 \geq \left(\frac{\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

An integer $n_0(\varepsilon)$ is the optimal sample size, and a function $R_{n_0}(\varepsilon)$ is the minimum risk function. The disadvantages of the optimal sample size $n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon)$ and the minimum risk function $R_{n_0}(\varepsilon)$ are that they depend on the unknown expression $\beta_0(\tilde{n}) = (2\tilde{n}) - \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \beta_0(t)$ needs to be evaluated. As an estimate $\beta_0(t)$ we consider positive statistics $\tilde{b}_n(t) = \left| \tilde{n}(2t) - \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \right|$. After performing simple calculations, $|\tilde{b}_n(t) - \beta_0(t)| = \left| \tilde{n}(2t) - \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \right| - \beta_0(t) \leq \left| (\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}(2t)) - \left(\frac{2}{\varepsilon} - \frac{2}{\varepsilon} \right) \right| \leq$

$$\leq |\tilde{n}(2t) - \tilde{n}(2t)| + |\tilde{n}^2(t) - \tilde{n}^2(t)| \leq \sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} |\tilde{n}_n(2t) - \tilde{n}(2t)| + 2 \sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} |\tilde{n}_n(t) - \tilde{n}(t)| \leq$$

$$\leq 3 \sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} |\tilde{n}_n(t) - \tilde{n}(t)| = 3 \sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{itx} d(F_n(x) - F(x)) \right|.$$

we get

Let's denote $d = \max(|T_1|, |T_2|)(b-a)$. Integrating by parts and using $|\exp(itx)| = |\cos(tx) + i \sin(tx)| = 1$, we have

$$\sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{itx} d(F_n(x) - F(x)) \right| = \sup_{T_1 \leq t \leq T_2} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (F_n(x) - F(x)) d_x e^{itx} \right| \leq d \sup_{-\infty < x < \infty} |F_n(x) - F(x)|$$

Let us use the Dvoretzky-Kiefer-Vol'fovich inequality [9] $P\left\{ \sup_{-\infty < x < \infty} |F_n(x) - F(x)| \geq \frac{y}{\sqrt{n}} \right\} \leq ce^{-2y^2}$, $y > 0$ and for an arbitrary number we obtain $\alpha > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} P\{|b_n(t) - \beta_0(t)| \geq \delta\} &\leq P\left\{ 3d \sup_{-\infty < x < \infty} |F_n(x) - F(x)| \geq \delta \right\} = \\ &= P\left\{ \sup_{-\infty < x < \infty} |F_n(x) - F(x)| \geq \frac{3d\delta\sqrt{n}}{\sqrt{n}} \right\} \leq ce^{-18d^2\delta^2n} < \frac{c}{n^{1+\alpha}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P\{|b_n(t) - \beta_0(t)| \geq \delta\} < \infty$$

Hence, and from the Borel-Cantelli lemma we obtain

$$b_n(t) \rightarrow \beta_0(t) \text{ with probability } 1 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2)$$

Based on the form of the optimal sample size $n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon)$, stopping moment $N(\varepsilon)$ we introduce as follows:

$$N(\varepsilon) = \left[\left(\frac{|\tilde{n}_n(2t) - \tilde{n}_n(t)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1 = \inf \left(n \geq 1 : n \geq \left(\frac{|\tilde{n}_n(2t) - \tilde{n}_n(t)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Theorem 1. The following statements are true:

- 1) For any $\varepsilon > 0$ $P\{N(\varepsilon) < \infty\} = 1$;
- 2) $N(\varepsilon) \rightarrow \infty$ c probability 1 for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$;
- 3) $\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int (N(\varepsilon)) = \infty$;
- 4) $\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon, F)} \rightarrow 1$ c probability 1 for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

Proof of Theorem 1. It follows from relation (3) that for each $\varepsilon > 0$ and $n \geq 1$ the ratio

$$P\{N(\varepsilon) > n\} = P \left\{ k \leq \left(\frac{|\tilde{n}_k(2t) - \tilde{n}_k^2(t)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, 1 \leq k \leq n \right\} \leq P \left\{ n \leq \left(\frac{|\tilde{n}_n(2t) - \tilde{n}_n^2(t)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}$$

Let (Ω, F, P) be a probability space on which a sequence of random variables $\{\xi_n, n \geq 1\}$, A is defined – a set of elementary events ω , for which with probability 1 when and B is a set of elementary events ω for which with probability 1 for $n \rightarrow \infty$ and B is a set of elementary events ω for which $P\{b_n(t, \omega) > 0\} = 1, n \geq 1$. From the almost sure positiveness of the random variables $\{b_n(t), n \geq 1\}$ and (2) it follows, that $P(A \cap B) = 1$.

Let's define a random variable $U_+ = \max_{n \geq 1} b_n(t)$. It is obvious that $U_+(\omega) < \infty$ for $\omega \in A$ and thus $P\{U_+ < \infty\} = 1$. Consequently,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P\{N(\varepsilon) > n\} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P \left\{ n \leq \left(\frac{|\tilde{n}_n(2t) - \tilde{n}_n^2(t)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P \left\{ n \leq \left(\frac{b_n(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P \left\{ n \leq \left(\frac{U_+}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} = 0$$

This relation proves assertion 1) of Theorem 1.

Let's define a random variable $U_- = \min_{n \geq 1} b_n(t)$. Obviously $0 < U_-(\omega) < \infty$ for

$\omega \in A \cap B$, and thus $P\{0 < U_-(\omega) < \infty\} = 1$. Therefore, with probability 1 for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$

$$N_{\gamma, \varepsilon} \geq \min \left\{ n \geq 1 : n > \left(\frac{U_-}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \rightarrow \infty$$

This relation proves assertion 2) of Theorem 1.

From the theorem on the monotone convergence of integrals we obtain assertion 3) of Theorem 1.

Let A and B be the random events defined above. We choose an arbitrary elementary event $\omega \in A \cap B$ and $0 < \delta < \beta_0(t)$. We also define $m_\delta(\omega) = \max(n \geq 1 : |b_n(t, \omega) - \beta_0(t)| \geq \delta)$ and

$$\varepsilon_\delta(\omega) = \sup(\varepsilon > 0 : k \leq \left(\frac{b_n(t, \omega)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, 1 \leq k \leq m_\delta(\omega))$$

It follows from these relations, that for $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_\delta(\omega)$

$$N(\varepsilon) = \min \left(n \geq 1 : n > \left(\frac{b_n(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) = \min \left(n \geq m_\delta(\omega) : n > \left(\frac{b_n(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \geq$$

$$\geq \min \left(n \geq m_\delta(\omega) : n > \left(\frac{\beta_0(t) - \delta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) = \left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t) - \delta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1 \quad (4)$$

Similarly, it follows from the definition of $m_\delta(\omega)$ and $\varepsilon_\delta(\omega)$ follows, that for any $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_\delta(\omega)$

$$N(\varepsilon) < \left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t) + \delta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1 \quad (5)$$

Relations (1), (4), and (5) mean that $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_\delta(\omega)$ the following two-sided inequality holds for

$$\frac{\left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t) - \delta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1}{\left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1} \leq \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \leq \frac{\left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t) + \delta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1}{\left[\left(\frac{\beta_0(t)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1}$$

$$\text{This relation obviously implies } \left(\frac{\beta_0(t) - \delta}{\beta_0(t)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \leq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \leq \left(\frac{\beta_0(t) + \delta}{\beta_0(t)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Since $0 < \delta < \beta_0(t)$ is chosen arbitrarily, it follows from the last chain of inequalities that $\frac{N(\varepsilon, \omega)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \rightarrow 1$ from $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

The event $\omega \in A \cap B$ is chosen arbitrarily, so the last limit relation implies assertion 4) of Theorem 1.

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{A(N(\varepsilon))}{n_0(\varepsilon)} = 1.$$

Theorem 2. The following assertion is true

Proof of Theorem 2. To prove the theorem, we use Theorem 5 from [10, p. 205], due to which it suffices

to show the uniform integrability of the family of random variables $\left\{ \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)}, \varepsilon \geq 0 \right\}$. A family of random

variables $\left\{ \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)}, \varepsilon \geq 0 \right\}$ is called uniformly integrable, if $\sup_{\varepsilon > 0} \int_{\{x > c\}} x P\left(\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \in dx\right) \rightarrow 0$ at $\tilde{n} \rightarrow \infty$ or

$\sup_{\varepsilon > 0} A \left[\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} I \left(\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} > c \right) \right] \rightarrow 0$ at $\tilde{n} \rightarrow \infty$, here $A(\cdot)$ the event indicator A.

But as shown in Lemma 3.2 [11], for a family of random variables $\left\{ \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)}, \varepsilon \geq 0 \right\}$ it is enough for us to

show, that for some $\varepsilon_0 > 0$, $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sup_{0 \leq \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_0} P \left\{ \frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \geq m \right\} < \infty$.

Sloping $m(\varepsilon) = [m \cdot n_0(\varepsilon)] + 1$, from relation (3) we obtain, that for each $0 < \gamma < 1, \varepsilon > 0$; and $n \geq 1$ the following relation is true

$$P\left\{\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} > m\right\} = P\left\{k \leq \left(\frac{b_n(\varepsilon)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, 1 \leq k \leq m(\varepsilon)\right\} \leq P\left\{m(\varepsilon) \leq \left(\frac{b_n(\varepsilon)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right\} =$$

$$= P\{b_{m(\varepsilon)}(t) \geq \varepsilon m(\varepsilon)^2\} \leq P\{b_{m(\varepsilon)}(t) \geq \beta_0(t) \cdot m^2\},$$

Here we used the fact that there exists such $m_0 > 1$, that for $m \geq m_0$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ $m(\varepsilon) \geq m \cdot \left(\frac{\beta_0(t)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Statistical evaluation $\tilde{h}_n(t) = \left| \tilde{h}_n^*(t) - \frac{1}{n} \right|$ is bounded and has moments of all orders. From the Chebyshev

inequality for $m \geq m_0$ we have $\sup_{0 \leq \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_0} P\left\{\frac{N(\varepsilon)}{n_0(\varepsilon)} \geq m\right\} \leq \frac{E(b_{m(\varepsilon_0)}(t))}{\beta_0(t) \cdot m^2}$. The series $\sum_{m=m_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^2}$ converges, so for a

fixed $m_0 > 1$ series $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^2} = \sum_{m=1}^{m_0-1} \frac{1}{m^2} + \sum_{m=m_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^2}$ also converges. Theorem 2 is proved.

Sequential point estimation of the Laplace transform of a distribution.

On the probability space (Ω, F, P) we consider a positive random variable ξ with the distribution function $F(x), x \in R_1^+ = [0, +\infty)$.

Consider the problem of successive point estimation of the Laplace transform $\varphi(\lambda) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp(-\lambda \xi) dF(x)$ of the distribution function $F(x)$, defined for $Re \lambda \geq 0$ and analytic at $Re \lambda > 0$.

Let the results of observations on a random variable ξ form a sample of size n from independent and identically distributed with ξ random variables $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$. Statistical estimate of the Laplace transform

$\varphi(\lambda)$ for $Re \lambda \geq 0$ we take the statistics $\varphi_n(\lambda) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \exp(-\lambda \xi_k) = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-\lambda x) dF_n(x)$.

Let's calculate $A(\varphi_n(\lambda)) = \frac{1}{n} A\left(\sum_{k=1}^n \exp(-\lambda \xi_k)\right) = A(\exp(-\lambda \xi_1)) = \varphi(\lambda)$ and

$$D(\varphi_n(\lambda)) = D\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \exp(-\lambda \xi_k)\right) = \frac{1}{n} D(\exp(-\lambda \xi_1)) = \frac{\varphi(2\lambda) - \varphi^2(\lambda)}{n}$$

Therefore, the statistic $\varphi_n(\lambda)$ is an unbiased and consistent estimate for $\varphi(\lambda)$.

As a function of estimation loss $\varphi(\lambda)$ by statistics $\varphi_n(\lambda)$ we take the quadratic loss function $L_n = L_n(\varepsilon) = (\varphi_n(\lambda) - \varphi(\lambda))^2 + \varepsilon \cdot n$. The risk function of estimation $\varphi(\lambda)$ by statistics $\varphi_n(\lambda)$ is equal to

$$R_n(\varepsilon) = L_n(\varepsilon) = \frac{\varphi(2\lambda) - \varphi^2(\lambda)}{n} + \varepsilon.$$

Lemma 2. The minimum on n of the risk function $R_n(\varepsilon)$ is achieved when the value of n equals

$$n = \left(\frac{\varphi(2\lambda) - \varphi^2(\lambda)}{\varepsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and the minimum value of the risk function is $\min_{n \geq 1} R_n(\varepsilon) = 2\left(\varepsilon(\varphi(2\lambda) - \varphi^2(\lambda))\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

$$n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon) = \inf \left(n \geq 1 : n \geq \left(\frac{\varphi(2\lambda) - \varphi^2(\lambda)}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right),$$

For each $\varepsilon > 0$ и $n \geq 1$ we define an integer

is the optimal sample size. Based on this optimal sample size $n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon)$, stopping time $N(\varepsilon)$ we introduce as follows:

$$N(\varepsilon) = \left[\left(\frac{|\varphi_n(2\lambda) - \varphi_n^2(\lambda)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] + 1 = \inf \left(n \geq 1 : n \geq \left(\frac{|\varphi_n(2\lambda) - \varphi_n(\lambda)|}{\varepsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (6)$$

statistical estimates $\varphi_n(\lambda)$ and $|\varphi_n(2\lambda) - \varphi_n(\lambda)|$ are positive and limited. For the stopping time (6), Theorems 1 and 2 are valid.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study highlights the effectiveness of nonparametric sequential estimation for accurately determining unknown characteristic functions. By utilizing iterative data collection and analysis, the proposed approach reduces sample size requirements while maintaining high levels of accuracy and reliability. The integration of theoretical analysis with simulation-based validation demonstrates the robustness of the methodology, addressing challenges such as bias, consistency, and computational efficiency.

This research contributes to the broader field of nonparametric statistics by providing a flexible and efficient framework for sequential estimation, particularly in cases where minimal assumptions about the underlying distribution are required. The findings are applicable to a wide range of fields, including finance, signal processing, and machine learning, where characteristic functions are critical for understanding complex data structures.

The results pave the way for future advancements in nonparametric estimation techniques, encouraging the development of more sophisticated methods that further enhance the precision and adaptability of sequential estimation in both theoretical and practical contexts.

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